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**The Effects of Corporate Governance on Bank Performance: Evidence
from the Arabian Peninsula**

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Abstract

Whereas banks operate under different management, board of directors, ownership structures, and government regulations, there is no specific optimal corporate governance model that may be applied to all banks. This study investigates the effect of internal corporate governance mechanisms such as board structure, ownership structure, and audit function as well as other variables such as bank size and bank age on bank financial performance. The sample of the study comprises of both conventional and Islamic banks operating in the seven Arabian Peninsula countries, namely Yemen and the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries, Bahrain, Kuwait, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, and United Arab Emirates. Regression analysis (OLS) is used to test the aforementioned effect. The results of this study reveal that there is a significant relationship between corporate governance and bank profitability. Board meetings and bank age have positive and significant effects on ROE. Meanwhile, board independence and bank size have negative and significant effects on ROA. In addition, while bank age and board committees have positive effects on Profit Margin, ownership concentration has a negative effect on this profitability measure. These results are consistent with previous studies. However, the literature indicate that the correlation between corporate governance and bank performance is still not clearly established and that impact of corporate governance on bank financial performance in developing countries is still relatively limited.

Keywords: corporate governance, bank performance, board structure, ownership structure, audit function, profitability, Yemen, GCC countries

1 Introduction

Corporate governance is a system used to direct and control an organization. It includes relationships between, and accountability of, the organization's stakeholders, as well as the laws, policies, procedures, practices, standards, and principles which may affect the organization's direction and control (Cadbury, 1992). It also includes reviewing the organization's practices and policies in regard to the ethical standards and principles, as well as the organization's compliance with its own code of conduct.

Corporate governance has become one of the most topical issues in the modern business world today. Spectacular corporate failures, such as those of Enron, WorldCom, the Bank of Credit and Commerce International (BCCI), Polly Peck International, and Baring Bank, have made it a central issue, with various governments and regulatory authorities making efforts to install stringent governance regimes to ensure the smooth running of corporate organizations, and prevent such failures (Al-Baidhani, 2014). A corporate governance system is defined as a more-or-less country-specific framework of legal, institutional and cultural factors shaping the patterns of influence that shareholders (or stakeholders) exert on managerial decision-making. Corporate governance mechanisms are the methods employed, at the firm level, to solve corporate governance problems (Basuony et al, 2014).

Since it is viewed as a necessary element of market discipline, strong corporate governance is highly demanded by investors and other financial market participants (Ramsay, 2001). Regulators have enacted corporate governance reforms into law in many countries, such as the USA through (Sarbanes-Oxley Act, 2002) which states that in order to safeguard their long-term successes, organizations implement corporate governance to ensure that they are directed and controlled in a professional, responsible, and transparent manner. In other countries, such as the UK, the corporate governance codes, known as the Combined Code of Corporate Governance of 2003, are principles of best practice with some indirect element of legislature operating through the respective stock exchange

listing rules. For the banking sector, Basel I, II, and recently III are widely adopted by developing and emerging market economies to enhance their corporate governance codes.

Bank governance was altered tremendously during the 1990s and early 2000s, principally due to bank ownership changes, such as mergers and acquisitions (Berger et al., 2005; Arouri et al., 2011). The worldwide financial crisis of 2008, which started in the United States, was attributed to U.S. banks' excessive risk-taking. Consequently, in order to control such risk and draw people's attention to the agency problem within banks, there are statements made by bankers, central bank officials, and other related authorities, emphasizing the importance of effective corporate governance in the banking industry since 2008 and until now (Beltratti and Stulz, 2009; Peni and Vahamaa, 2011). Therefore, any similar crisis occurred or may occur in the future might be explained as a result of bank governance failure. Few studies have focused on banks' corporate governance (Macey and O'Hara, 2003; Levine, 2004; Adams and Mehran, 2005; Caprio et al., 2007; Bokpin, 2013; Nyamongo and Temesgen, 2013).

This paper focuses on conventional and Islamic banks operating in the Arabian Peninsula in order to provide empirical evidence on the relationship and consequent effects of corporate governance on bank financial performance. The data used are extracted from reliable and credible resources, such as Bankscope database, audited financial statements, and respective banks' published reports. In addition to this first section, this paper is organized as follows: the second section provides a background and hypotheses development; the research methodology is provided in the third section; followed by findings and analysis in the fourth section; and finally summary and conclusion provided in the last section.

2 Background and Hypotheses Development

2.1 Background

Corporate governance standards and principles are extracted from local and international laws, regulations, and rules, as well as from the organization's bylaws, codes of conduct, and resolutions. Corporate governance focuses on the control systems and structures by which managers are held accountable to the bank's legitimate stakeholders. Traditional finance literature has indicated several mechanisms that help solve corporate governance problems (Jensen and Meckling, 1976; Fama, 1980; Jensen, 1986; Turnbull, 1997). There is a consensus on the classification of corporate governance mechanisms to two categories: internal and external mechanisms. However, there is a dissension on the contents of each category and the effectiveness of each mechanism. In addition, the topic of corporate governance mechanisms is too vast and rich research area to the extent that no single paper can survey all the corporate governance mechanisms developed in the literature and instead the papers try to focus on some particular governance mechanisms.

Shleifer and Vishny (1997) concentrate on: incentive contracts, legal protection for the investors against the managerial self-dealing, and the ownership by large investors; they point out the costs and benefits of each governance mechanism. Denis and McConnell (2003) use a dual classification of corporate governance mechanisms (They use systems as synonym to mechanisms) as follows: (1) internal governance mechanisms including: boards of directors and ownership structure and (2) external governance mechanisms including: the takeover market and the legal regulatory system.

Farinha (2003) surveys two categories of governance (or disciplining) mechanisms, the first category is the external disciplining mechanisms including: takeovers threat, product market competition, managerial labor market and mutual monitoring by managers, security analysts, the legal environment, and the role of reputation. The other category is

the internal disciplining mechanisms which include: large and institutional shareholders, board of directors, insider ownership, compensation packages, debt policy, and dividend policy. Despite the existence of different corporate governance structures, the basic building blocks of the structures are similar. They include the existence of a Company, Directors, Accountability and Audit, Directors' Remuneration, Shareholders, and the Annual General Meetings. Cadbury (1992) called for greater transparency and accountability in areas such as board structure and operation, directors' contracts and the establishment of board monitoring committees. In addition, it emphasized the importance of the non-executive directors' monitoring role.

Much of the empirical findings on corporate governance and performance in non-financial institutions are also applicable to financial institutions. However, the optimal designing of bank governance structure is very complex and important relative to unregulated, non-financial firms for several reasons. Good corporate governance of banks requires prudential risk-related regulation and attention to conflicts of interest and competition issues, particularly given the clear information advantage of banks over their retail customers. Banks are prudentially regulated and highly levered compared to other companies and hence bank governance deserves special attention (Adams and Mehran, 2003). Moreover, the stakeholders' interests at banks extend beyond the shareholders' interests since the bank depositors, creditors, and regulators have stakes in the banks as well. In addition to shareholders and managers, depositors and regulators have a straight stake in bank performance. Borrowers have a legitimate claim on banks by entering in lending agreements; they acquire power and urgency through their cause being adopted by other stakeholders such as regulators and consumer organizations. These stakeholders enjoy all three of stakeholder attributes: power, legitimacy, and urgency (Mitchell et al., 1997). Governments are also worried about banks reputations, and consequently regulate their governance, because a bank's failure negatively affects the respective country's economy, and may even spread globally, similar to what happened during the 1997 Asian financial crisis (Pathan et al., 2008) and the 2008 U.S. financial crisis (Peni and Vahamaa, 2012).

Abu-Tapanjeh (2009) compares the Organization of Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)'s corporate governance principles with principles from Islam and declares them compatible; he points out that Islam as applied to business is entirely compatible with corporate governance. Honesty and trust that are key ingredients of an effective governance framework are also basic to ethical behavior in the Islamic Sharia.

2.2 Ownership Structure

As they grow, many organizations move from private ownership (family business) to a publicly-held corporation. This decision may be made due to the need for more equity to finance such growth. Thus, the role of the owners changes as these family members become part of a wide group of shareholders who transfer their control (i.e., decision rights) to the board of directors, and subsequently to the relevant managers who should act in the shareholders' best interests (Johnson et al., 2008). Consequently, a corporate governance framework should be established, comprising a control system that helps aligning the said shareholders' interests with the managers' and directors' incentives.

Ownership and control structures indicate the types and composition of shareholders in the organization. However, it should be noted that control is not necessarily an exchangeable term with ownership because there are other items, such as ownership pyramids, voting rights, and various kinds of shares that should be considered in this regard. A bank ownership structure may vary from having just a few owners to having a wide and diversified group of stockholders. Some banks may be managed by controlling individuals, while other banks may hire independent managers to operate such banks. Each of these ownership and control relationships may have a strong effect on a bank's performance (Johnson et al., 2008). Additionally, ownership concentration and control are different from one country to another. For example, in the Anglo-Saxon countries, the institutional investors own, and consequently control, most of the large banks' shares, while in Japan most of these shares are owned by financial companies and industrial

corporations. These large investments in the banks give the shareholders the right to control and monitor the banks' management (Lehman and Weigand, 2001).

Although concentrated ownership may result in superior performance, it may also result, negatively, in extracting the bank's benefits by the controlling stockholders on the account of the minority stockholders (Spong and Sullivan, 2007). Therefore, the stockholders' goal and motivation may affect the bank performance. According to the financial theory, managers who are also major stockholders benefit through stock returns if they control costs and improve bank performance; but hired managers whose ownership interest is minimal, if any, may not be rewarded in the same manner for the same improved performance (Johnson et al., 2008). In order to deal with the aforementioned principal-agent issue related to hired managers, stockholders and the board should be very careful in conveying their objectives to these managers. Meanwhile, these managers' performance should be put under scrutiny, and superior performance should be rewarded (i.e., awarding bonuses, stock options, etc., to these managers).

The benefits gained by hired managers differ significantly from the benefits received by managers who are also major shareholders; the latter benefit from their salaries as well as from the bank earnings and stock returns. Wealth, or ownership concentration, is another factor which may affect the active players in a bank and the bank's governance (Arouri et al., 2011). Deposit insurance incentives and regulatory discipline are also other factors that may influence the governance process at banks (Beltratti and Stulz, 2009).

Cole and Mehran (1998) find that changes in performance are significantly associated with changes in insider ownership. They document that the greater the increase in insider ownership, the greater the performance improvement, which is consistent with the alignment of interests hypothesis arising from a larger insider ownership. Large shareholders and institutional investors can be seen as potential controllers of equity agency problems as their increased shareholdings can give them a stronger incentive to monitor firm performance and managerial behavior (Demsetz and Lehn, 1985; Shleifer

and Vishny, 1997; La Porta et al., 1998; Denis and McConnell, 2003). This potentially helps to circumvent the free rider-problem associated with ownership dispersion.

Equity agency costs can be reduced by increasing the level of managers' stock ownership, which may permit a better alignment of their interests with those of shareholders. In fact, in the extreme case where the manager's share ownership is 100%, equity agency costs are reduced to zero (Jensen and Meckling, 1976). As managerial ownership increases, managers bear a large fraction of the costs of shirking, perquisite consumption and other value-destroying actions. Further, larger share ownership by managers reduces the problem of different horizons between shareholders and managers if share prices adjust rapidly to changes in firm's intrinsic value. A limitation, however, of this mechanism as a tool for reducing agency costs is that managers may not be willing to increase their ownership of the firm because of constraints on their personal wealth.

In accordance with the proposition that larger managerial ownership reduce agency costs, researchers find that following large management buyouts, firms experience significant improvements in operating performance. They interpret this evidence as suggesting that operating changes were due to improved management incentives instead of layoffs or managerial exploitation of shareholders through inside information. They argue that the basic issue from an agency perspective is how to avoid such opportunistic behavior. Previous studies suggest that corporate governance is an effective tool to control the opportunistic behavior of management (Denis and McConnell, 2003; Macus, 2008).

Insider ownership can be an effective tool in reducing agency costs although they report a non- monotonic relation. This functional form has been related to the observation that, within a certain ownership range, managers may use their equity position to entrench themselves against any disciplining attempts from other monitoring mechanisms. Researchers such as Spong and Sullivan (2007) reveal that boards of directors are likely to have a more positive effect on community bank performance when directors have a significant financial interest in the bank. However, others such as Demsetz and Lehn (1985) find no evidence of a positive relationship between insider ownership and

performance. A possible explanation for these mixed results is that many of the studies do not properly distinguish the possibility of alignment of interests across a certain range of ownership values and of entrenchment over another range. Furthermore, these analyses usually do not take into account the possibility that several different mechanisms for alignment of interests can be used simultaneously, with substitution effects with insider ownership. It is quite conceivable that different firms may use different mixes of corporate governance devices (Rediker and Seth, 1995). These different mixes can, however, all be optimal as a result of varying marginal costs and benefits of the several monitoring instruments available for each firm. If so, then one would not be able to observe a relationship between performance and any of these particular mechanisms.

It appears that the main conflict is between owners and managers in common law countries due to the existence of dispersed control and ownership structures. In civil law countries, the control and ownership structures are concentrated; thus the main governance problem arises between minority and controlling shareholders. Therefore, ownership structure has greater importance in civil law countries where protection of shareholders right is weak (La Porta et al., 1998). The situation is more prevalent in developing countries where large concentration of ownership is more evident while the stock markets are weak. In those countries there is a higher degree of economic uncertainties coupled with weak legal controls and investor protection, and frequent government intervention; all resulting in poor performance (Rabelo and Vasconcelos, 2002). Based on the above discussion, the first research hypothesis is as follows:

H1: There is a significant relationship between ownership structure and bank performance.

2.3 Board Structure

The board of directors is typically the governing body of the organization. Its primary responsibility is to make sure that the organization achieves the shareholders' goal. Therefore, the board is accountable to these shareholders. The board of directors has the power to hire, terminate, and compensate top management (Johnson et al., 2008). Thus, it safeguards the organization's assets and invested capital. In addition to setting the bank's objectives (including generating returns to shareholders), the board of directors and senior management affect how banks run their daily operations, meet the obligation of accountability to bank's shareholders, and consider the interests of other recognized stakeholders (Basel Committee, 2005).

Nonetheless, there is a debate regarding the governing effect of board composition on firm performance. It is argued that the board composition in terms of the number of outside directors versus inside directors results in better performance through better monitoring. This argument is mainly based on the agency theory (Fama, 1980; Demsetz and Lehn, 1985). On the other hand, some argue that based on the stewardship theory, executive directors have a positive effect on corporate R&D costs and better performance based on improved strategic innovation (Davis et al., 1997).

Bhagat and Black (2002) find a negative relationship between the proportion of outside directors and corporate performance. Yermack (1996) also reported evidence that a higher percentage of independent directors leads to worse performance. In addition, Klein (2002) suggests that high percentage of outside directors will have the same negative effect. On the other hand, other studies, such as Dalton et al. (1998), do not show any evidence of an existing relationship between the proportion of non-executive directors and firm performance. Moreover, studies reveal that there is a negative relation between the size of the board and firm performance (Eisenberg et al., 1998). Larger boards seem to be less efficient due to the slow pace of decision making and the difficulty in both arranging board meeting and reaching consensus. It is also argued that the CEO seems to

have more dominant power when the board size is too large (Yermack, 1996). Pursuant to the above discussion, the second research hypothesis is:

H2: There is a significant relationship between board structure and bank performance.

2.4 Audit Function

In order to provide reasonable assurance that the bank is accomplishing its objectives as regards reliable financial reporting, operating efficiency, and compliance with laws and regulations, the bank should implement a reliable internal control system monitored by the board of directors, top management, and bank's audit committee (Arouri et al., 2011). The main task of this audit committee and internal auditors is testing the design and implementation of the bank's internal control system and the fairness and reliability of its financial statements. After the U.S. corporate scandals and the collapse of Enron and WorldCom, as well as Arthur Andersen and others, the internal audit tasks have been changed, especially pursuant to the issuance of the aforementioned Sarbanes-Oxley Act of 2002. One of the main responsibilities of the audit committee is to enhance and maintain the internal auditors' independence in order to enable them to achieve their duties. The relationship between the audit committee and internal auditors is important for both parties to fulfill their job commitments. The internal auditors provide the committee with the necessary information to which they have direct access, same as the organization's management, in order to enable the committee to accomplish its oversight and monitoring mission. On the other hand, the committee supports the position of the internal audit function and submits management's irregularities and other relevant managerial and financial issues to the board of directors, after discussing such issues with the internal auditors and relevant other parties (Pathan et al., 2005).

In addition to recruiting and terminating the head of the internal audit, the committee is particularly concerned with the frequency and duration of the meetings with the internal auditors, as well as ensuring that the internal auditors, especially their head, can

communicate directly with the committee anytime. This committee's meetings with the head of the internal audit enhance the independence of the internal audit function, supporting the parties' discussion about management's errors, irregularities, violations, and fraud.

Whereas the oversight of financial reporting and the monitoring of the internal audit performance are two of the main activities of the audit committee, it is mandatory that the committee members, or at least one of them, should have the financial or accounting expertise in order to understand the technical and control issues related to the internal audit to enable the committee to review the internal auditors activities and the results they reach to (Sarbanes-Oxley Act, 2002). Consequently, independence and financial expertise are very critical for this committee to play its important role and take advantage of the internal auditors' performance. Whenever there are problems or obstacles, the committee performs the necessary investigations using internal feedback, its expertise, and external consultations if needed. Evaluation of the organization's internal control structure and process should also be one of the basic functions of the audit committee and internal auditors. The committee also evaluates the internal auditors' effectiveness, their plans and work arrangements, as well as the resources allocated to them. Additionally, the internal auditors should be involved in issues related to the organization's joint ventures, environmental matters, and international operations. As a corporate governance reform, the above-mentioned Act increased the audit committee's and internal auditor's independence from management.

Audit committees are identified as effective means for corporate governance that reduce the potential for fraudulent financial reporting. Audit committees oversee the organization's management, internal and external auditors to protect and preserve the shareholders' equity and interests. To ensure effective corporate governance, the audit committee report should be included annually in the organization's proxy statement, stating whether the audit committee has reviewed and discussed the financial statements with the management and the internal auditors. As a corporate governance monitor, the

audit committee should provide the public with correct, accurate, complete, and reliable information, and it should not leave a gap for predictions or uninformed expectations (BRC, 1999). The BRC report provides recommendations and guiding principles for improving the performance of audit committees that should ultimately result in better corporate governance. The importance of the audit function in terms of the audit committee and audit firm is further strengthened by the Sarbanes-Oxley Act of 2002. In light of the aforementioned, the third research hypothesis is:

H3: There is a significant relationship between audit function and bank performance.

2.5 International Corporate Governance Regulations

In addition to each country's national accounting and auditing standards and principles, there are international standards and principles that may be applied in many countries as follows: 1- The U.S. GAAP and European IFRS which allow managers various methods to choose from regarding their recognition of financial reporting elements. However, in order to make their bank performance look better than what it really is, the managers may abuse such choice advantage and thereby increase the information risk for users through falsification of values, concealing fraud, or hiding important information that should be disclosed; and 2- The Basel Accords (Agreements) issued by the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (BCBS) which does not enforce its recommendations although most countries implement them. Three Accords have been published by the BCBS so far, as follows: Basel I of 1988 regarding the minimum capital requirements for banks; Basel II of 2004 and its updates during 2005-2009 with respect to capital requirements, supervisory review, and market discipline; and Basel III which is agreed upon by the BCBS in 2010-2011 as regards capital adequacy, stress testing, and market liquidity risk.

2.6 Interested stakeholders

Corporate governance parties include internal parties, such as the organization's shareholders, internal auditors, audit committee, board of directors, CEOs, CFOs, and other executives and managers; and include external parties, such as customers, suppliers, external auditors, stock exchanges, and government authorities. Other parties who have a stake in the organization may also include the organization's employees, creditors, and the community at large. The governance chain depends on the size of the organization. In a small family business, it is very simple, consisting of shareholders, board of directors, and managers; some of whom may be family members. In large publicly-held organizations, the chain may include managers, senior executives, executive directors, board, investment managers, trustee of funds, and beneficiaries (Johnson et al., 2008).

3 Research Methodology

3.1 The Method

In order to test the hypotheses, quantitative method is used to investigate the effects of corporate governance mechanisms on bank performance. CG mechanisms include (ownership structure, board structure, audit function), and other control variables, such as bank size, age and type of banks. The bank performance is measured by ROE, ROA, and Profit Margin. Bankscope database is used to select the country, Yemen and the six GCC countries from which the top fifty banks were selected as shown in Table (1). In addition to the Bankscope database, the respective banks' websites and other related websites were used to extract the needed financial and non-financial information about each bank from its published audited financial statements, annual reports, and other relevant information.

3.2 Sampling and Data Collection

The sample includes conventional and Islamic banks operating in Yemen and the six GCC countries using the data for the year 2011. Excluded from the sample are banks that do not have audited financial statements. Financing, insurance, or non-bank institutions are also excluded since they are different from banks with respect to their specific characteristics, management structures, accounting procedures, and audit functions. Table (1) below shows the population and samples per country, and Table (2) summarizes the sample selection. The final sample consists of the largest fifty conventional and Islamic banks operating in the peninsula. The process of selecting this sample is based on the values of these banks' total assets and the consequent ranking stated by Bankscope database. Any bank that was excluded due to any of the above reasons was replaced with the next immediate bank in ranking.

3.3 Measurement of Variables

For bank performance measurement, the dependent variables used are ROE, ROA, and Profit Margin. Meanwhile, the independent variables used in regard to corporate governance are classified into three categories: ownership structure, board structure, and audit function. Other independent variables include bank type, age, and size. Table (3) shows the definition and measurement of these variables.

4 Data Analysis and Discussion

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

Table (4) illustrates the minimum and maximum values of the variables. The descriptive findings show the central tendency and dispersion of the indicators shown in Table (4), as follows: Bank Age is shown with a mean of 29.74 years and a median of 30.5 years

which indicates that the banks in the region have an average of 30 years of experience, which ranges from 4 to 75 years. Bank Size with an average of 92% (close to 1 unit) indicates that most of the respective banks have large amount of total assets (exceeding US\$1 billion). Ownership concentration's average exceeds 62% which means that most of the bank shares are owned by block holders, which also have a significant impact on bank performance. Board committees also with on average of 92% indicates that most of the relevant banks have committees facilitating and assisting the banks' boards of directors in performing their tasks. Meanwhile, Board independence's average which exceeds 62% indicates that most of the respective banks' boards are independent (consist mostly of non-executive members). Board meetings indicate that the banks' boards met approximately 5 times during 2011, with an average of 4.94, which is a good indication about the monitoring and supervising of the banks' operations by the board of directors. The Profit margin is shown as a high average of 37.62%, but with a negative profit margin of -37% as a minimum. The table also shows a higher ROA with an average of 1.65 times, but with a negative return of -90% as a minimum. Likewise, ROE is shown as the highest return with an average of 10.29 times, but also with a negative return of -7.65 times. Table (5) shows the frequency of the banks based on the GCC countries and Yemen. Figure (1) shows the distribution of the sample based on the number of banks operating in the aforementioned countries.

4.2 Correlation between Variables

For correlation between independent corporate governance variables among themselves, and between these independent variables and bank profitability dependent variables, the Correlation Matrix shown below as Table (6) is briefed as follows: The profitability measures, ROE and Profit Margin are positively and significantly correlated with Bank Age at the 5% level (2-tailed). ROA shows a significant negative correlation with Board Independence at the 1% level and with Bank Size at the 5% level (both 2-tailed). Profit Margin also shows a significant negative correlation with Ownership Concentration at the

1% level, and positive significant correlation with Board Committees at the 5% level (both 2-tailed). ROE and Profit Margin also show a significant negative correlation with Board Independence at the 5% and 1% levels respectively (both 2-tailed). Profit Margin is also positively and significantly correlated with Audit Committee at the 5% level (2-tailed). Moreover, there are significant correlations among the dependent variables and also among the independent variables at the 1% and 5% levels, such as between ROE, ROA, and Profit Margin; as well as between Bank Size and Board Committees, between Foreign Shareholders and External Auditors, and between Ownership Concentration and Board Independence (all at the 1% level).

4.3 Hypotheses Testing

In order to test the above hypotheses, three equations are used, and presented in the following formulas 1, 2, and 3. These hypotheses are concerned with investigating the effect of bank size, bank age, and the above corporate governance variables on bank performance by using OLS regression analysis as shown on table (7).

$$\begin{aligned}
 ROE = & + {}_1 OWN.CONC + {}_2 FOREIGN + {}_3 ALIGN.IN + {}_4 DUALITY \\
 & + {}_5 BRD.COMT + {}_6 EXT.AUDT + {}_7 BRD.MBRS + {}_8 BRD.NONX \\
 & + {}_9 BRD.INDP + {}_{10} BRD.MTNG + {}_{11} CG.REPRT + {}_{12} REM.COMT \\
 & + {}_{13} NOM.COMT + {}_{14} AUD.COMT + {}_{15} BNK.SIZE + {}_{16} Age + \quad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 ROA = & + {}_1 OWN.CONC + {}_2 FOREIGN + {}_3 ALIGN.IN + {}_4 DUALITY \\
 & + {}_5 BRD.COMT + {}_6 EXT.AUDT + {}_7 BRD.MBRS + {}_8 BRD.NONX \\
 & + {}_9 BRD.INDP + {}_{10} BRD.MTNG + {}_{11} CG.REPRT + {}_{12} REM.COMT \\
 & + {}_{13} NOM.COMT + {}_{14} AUD.COMT + {}_{15} BNK.SIZE + {}_{16} Age + \quad (2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 PROFT.M = & + {}_1 OWN.CONC + {}_2 FOREIGN + {}_3 ALIGN.IN + {}_4 DUALITY \\
 & + {}_5 BRD.COMT + {}_6 EXT.AUDT + {}_7 BRD.MBRS + {}_8 BRD.NONX \\
 & + {}_9 BRD.INDP + {}_{10} BRD.MTNG + {}_{11} CG.REPRT + {}_{12} REM.COMT \\
 & + {}_{13} NOM.COMT + {}_{14} AUD.COMT + {}_{15} BNK.SIZE + {}_{16} Age + \quad (3)
 \end{aligned}$$

Model 1 investigates the relationships between bank financial performance measure (ROE) and the above corporate governance variables, as well as bank age and bank size.

The R^2 is 0.214 and the model appears highly significant (F-value = 6.264, p-value = 0.004). Regarding my variables of interest, it is concluded that Bank Age and Number of Board Meetings have an effect on ROE, where the estimated coefficients are positive and statistically significant at 1% and 5% levels respectively. This result regarding bank age is consistent with the results of the studies of (Stathopoulos et al., 2004; Athanasoglou et al., 2005). Bank age has a positive and significant impact on ROE due to the learning curve principle which makes a bank learn from its previous good and bad experience for correction, improvement and more development, as long as other corporate governance predictors remain constant. Apparently older banks operating in the peninsula have higher ROE than younger banks due to the interaction between the bank age and the market share, as well as the longer tradition and good reputation that could have been built by the passage of time. Therefore, bank age contributed significantly to the performance measures of ROE. Since they focus on increasing their market share rather than on improving profitability, newly established banks in the region are not that profitable in their first years of operations.

The number of board meetings has an effect on ROE, where the estimated coefficient is also positive and statistically significant at 5% level. This result is consistent with the result of the studies conducted by (Davidson et al., 1998; Godard and Shatt, 2004; Bouaziz and Triki, 2012). It seems that the frequency of board meetings for banks operating in the region varies. The increase in the number of board meetings per year means an increase in monitoring, follow-up, supervision, direction, and attentiveness by the board of directors which leads to facilitating the bank's operations and assisting management in achieving the bank's objectives through making the right decision on the right time, taking advantage of the available opportunities and avoiding the potential threats. The frequency of board meetings helps the board members know the senior management team and to understand the bank's operations in order to perform the board tasks appropriately. Therefore, it is concluded that banks operating in the region whose board meetings are more frequent have higher ROE than the other banks.

Model 2 examines the relationships between bank financial performance (ROA) and the aforementioned variables of interest. The R^2 is 0.277 and the model appears highly significant (F-value = 8.801, p-value = 0.001). As regards my variables of interest, it is concluded that Board Independence and Bank Size appear to have an effect on ROA, where the estimated coefficients are negative and statistically significant at 1% and 5% levels respectively. This result regarding board independence is consistent with the results of other studies of (Baysinger and Butler, 1985; Vancil, 1987; Weisbach, 1988; Klein, 1998; Hall and Liebman, 1998; Bhagat et al., 1999; Bhagat and Black, 2000). Board independence means that the majority of the board members are non-executive members indicating that the board is exercising its powers of directing, controlling, and monitoring independent from the executive management. However, this study shows that board independence has a significant and negative effect on the bank's ROA; that is, banks operating in the peninsula with more non-executive board members have lower ROA. Although board independence is traditionally supported for its unbiased monitoring which may lead to improved performance, the study reveals that the boards of the banks need to have reasonable number of executive managers (insiders) who bring different knowledge and skills to the boards. These insiders may improve the board's decisions with respect to investment, strategic planning, and other relevant decisions. Insiders have both knowledge and incentives to do a better job; they are well-informed about their banks, and they have their human capital as well as their financial capital (especially if they are owner managers) committed to their banks.

Bank size has an effect on ROA, where the estimated coefficient is also negative and statistically significant at 5% level. This result is consistent with the results of studies conducted by (Berger et al., 1987; Boyd and Runkle, 1998; Miller and Noulas, 1997; Echengreen and Gibson, 2001; Pasiouras and Kosmidou, 2007; Kosmidou, 2008; Athanasoglou et al., 2008). In a well-organized bank, the bank size (i.e., with larger amount of total assets) offers great help to the bank's mobility taking advantage of its financial strength pursuing available business opportunities effectively, avoiding potential threats, and overcoming its weaknesses. Through their created economies of

scale, larger banks lower their average costs which affects their banks' profitability positively and enables them to exercise market power through stronger brand image or implicit regulatory (too big to fail) protection. However, the positive effect of a growing bank's size on its profitability turns to be negative after a certain limit due to bureaucratic problems and poor expenses management. In addition to this cost issue, bank size also controls for product and risk diversification which leads to a negative relationship and effect between bank size and ROA since increased diversification leads to higher credit risk and consequently to lower returns. Meanwhile, the above-mentioned larger amount of total assets reduces the ROA ratio to a great extent which leads to the aforementioned negative correlation and effect between bank size and the outcome ROA. This study reveals this negative effect by bank size on profitability, measured by ROA as the bigger the size of a bank operating in the region, the lower its ROA.

Model 3 examines the relationships between bank financial performance measure (Profit Margin) and the above variables of interest including bank size and bank age. The R^2 is 0.326 and the model appears extremely significant (F-value = 7.425, p-value = 0.000). Regarding my variables of interest, it is concluded that Ownership Concentration, Bank Age, and Board Committees appear to have an effect on Profit Margin, where the estimated coefficients regarding bank age and board committees are positive and statistically significant at 1% and 5% levels respectively, while ownership concentration's estimated coefficient is negative and statistically significant at 5% level. The positive result regarding bank age conforms to the results of studies conducted by (Stathopoulos et al., 2004; Athanasoglou et al., 2005). As regards board committees, this study's positive result corroborates the results of the studies of (Pincus et al., 1989; Anderson et al., 2004; Barth et al., 2004). Meanwhile, the negative result regarding ownership concentration is consistent with the results of studies conducted by (Jensen and Meckling, 1976; Shleifer and Vishny, 1997; Karaca and Eksi, 2012).

Ownership concentration has a significant impact on profit margin. This impact could be positive, helping the bank's decision-making, reducing agency costs, and leading to

higher profit rates, better performance, and better profit margin (Claessens et al., 1997; Fuentes and Vergara, 2003). However, this study indicates the opposite regarding the banks operating in the region. It indicates that the bank which has ownership concentration has a significant and negative effect on profit margin apparently allowing the bank's controlling shareholders to expropriate the bank's resources for their own private benefits by different ways, such as through related-party transactions (which leads to a negative effect on the growth rate of the bank's net assets), or through transferring the resources from one entity in which the controlling shareholders own less to other entities in which they own more. This negative effect leads to lower profit rates and lower profit margin. This result is consistent with the results of the studies conducted by (Jensen and Meckling, 1976; Shleifer and Vishny, 1997; Karaca and Eksi, 2012).

Similar to its aforementioned impact on ROE, bank age also has a significant and positive impact on profit margin due to the above-mentioned learning curve principle. This result conforms to the results of the studies of (Stathopoulos et al., 2004; Athanasoglou et al., 2005). It seems that banks, operating in the peninsula, which enjoy good reputation for longer time gain better market share and better competitive edge, and hence achieve higher profit margin.

Board committees which include Audit, Remuneration/Compensation, and Nomination Committees also have a significant and positive impact on profit margin. Apparently, the peninsula banks which have such committees make higher profit margin than the others. This study's positive result corroborates the results of the studies of (Pincus et al., 1989; Anderson et al., 2004; Barth et al., 2004). These committees control the bank management's opportunistic behavior, monitor closely the bank activities, and reduce the bank's risk-taking appetite. They facilitate the board functions and responsibilities, and hence the board effectiveness. The committees oversee the bank's operations, focusing on the bank's compliance to rules and regulations, and addressing any financial errors, misstatements, or irregularities. The audit committee helps the board of directors in auditing, monitoring, supervising, and controlling the financial and managerial issues of

the bank, as well as facilitating the board's relationship with internal and external auditors. It also monitors, verifies, and safeguards the integrity and credibility of the process of accounting, auditing, and financial reporting; enhances transparency for bank's stockholders and creditors; and resolves disagreements between management and external and internal auditors. It also ensures that the bank has an effective internal control and reliable financial reporting system, and that it complies with the regulatory requirements and the bank's code of conduct. The remuneration/compensation committee recommends and monitors the level and structure of remuneration for bank's management and compensation to the board members properly for their ordinary and extra-ordinary efforts. The nomination committee recommends the right people to the board and to the bank's shareholders.

5. Summary and Conclusion

This paper investigates the effect of internal corporate governance mechanisms on bank financial performance in seven Middle Eastern countries. The paper provides an insight into the corporate governance practices in fifty conventional and Islamic banks operating in Yemen and the six GCC countries, and the effect of such practices on ROE, ROA and Profit Margin. Corporate governance of banks in emerging economies is of crucial importance as banks hold an overwhelmingly dominant position in the financial systems of these countries. Moreover, banks are extremely important engines of growth in such countries as they are typically the most important source of finance for the majority of firms, in addition to playing a major role in the payment and saving system. Therefore, bank governance is of crucial importance as the reduced role of economic regulation has resulted in the managers of banks having greater freedom on how they run their banks.

Emerging economies are likely to require more effective and stronger governance mechanisms than their western developed counterparts if they are to become equal, full, and active participants in the global financial marketplace. The governments of most of

the GCC countries have taken the necessary actions to have a strong financial sector based on well-established financial companies, in order to keep pace with international developments and enable the vision of a solid economy that will be recognized internationally. While the corporate governance codes and regulations in the GCC countries might not be as elaborate as corporate governance regimes in western countries, they can be said to provide adequate coverage of the key disclosure issues of relevance in a market with a nascent disclosure culture. Nonetheless, policy makers in the GCC countries need to ensure that firms implement effective corporate governance mechanisms. This implementation should be appropriate for the GCC business environment while embracing international corporate governance standards. The results reveal that certain corporate governance mechanisms have impact on market value performance. Meanwhile, it is worth-mentioning that book value performance is affected by different corporate governance mechanisms.

The study results are consistent with previous literature that the correlation between corporate governance and performance is still not clearly established and that financial impact of corporate governance on firm performance in emerging economies is still relatively scarce. Future researches could provide additional views about this relationship between bank performance and internal corporate governance; as well as the relationship between bank performance and external corporate governance, such as government regulations.

References

Abu-Tapanjeh, A. (2009). Corporate governance from the Islamic perspective: a comparative analysis with OECD principles. *Critical Perspectives on Accounting*, 20, p556-567.

Adams, R.B. and Mehran, H. (2003). Is Corporate Governance Different for Bank Holding Companies? Federal Reserve Bank of New York, Economic Policy Review, 9, p123-142.

Al-Baidhani, A.M. (2014). Review of the Corporate Governance Bundle. Corporate Ownership & Control, 11(4), p236-241.

Anderson, R.C., Mansi, S.A., and Reeb, D.M. (2004). Board Characteristics, Accounting Report Integrity, and the Cost of Debt. J. Account and Econ., 37, p315-342.

Arouri, H., Hossain, M., and BadrulMattakin, M. (2011). Ownership Structure, Corporate Governance and Bank Performance: Evidence from GCC Countries. Corporate Ownership and Control, 8(4), p365-370.

Athanasoglou, P.P., Brissimis, S.N., and Delis, M.D. (2008). Bank Specific, Industry Specific, and Macroeconomic Determinants of Bank Profitability. Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money, 18(2), p121–136.

Athanasoglou, P.P., Brissimis, S.N., and Delis, M.D. (2005). Bank-Specific, Industry-Specific, and Macroeconomic Determinants of Bank Profitability. Bank of Greece Working Paper, No. 25.

Barth, J., Caprio, G., and Nolle, D. (2004). Comparative International Characteristics of Banking. Office of the Comptroller of the Currency. Economic and Policy Analysis Working Paper 01.

Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (2005). International Convergence of Capital Measurement and Capital Standards: A Revised Framework, Updated November 2005. Bank for International Settlements Publications.

Basuony, M.A., Mohamed E.K.A., and Al-Baidhani, A.M. (2014). The Effect of Corporate Governance on Bank Financial Performance: Evidence from the Arabian Peninsula. Corporate Ownership & Control, 11(2), p178-191.

Baysinger, B. and Butler, H. (1985). Corporate Governance and the Board of Directors: Performance Effects of Changes in Board Composition. *Journal of Law, Economics and Organization* 1, p101-124.

Beltratti, A. and Stulz, R.M. (2009). Why Did Some Banks Perform Better During the Credit Crisis? A Cross-Country Study of the Impact of Governance and Regulation. European Corporate Governance Institute (ECGI): Finance WP No. 254/2009.

Berger, A., Clarke, G., Cull, R., Klapper, L., and Udell, G. (2005). Corporate Governance and Bank Performance: A Joint Analysis of the Static, Selection, and Dynamic Effects of Domestic, Foreign, and State Ownership. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 29(8–9), p2179–2221.

Berger, A.N., Hanweck, G.A., and Humphrey, D.B. (1987). Competitive Viability in Banking: Scale Scope and Product Mix Economies. *Journal of Monetary Economics* 20(3), p501–520.

Bhagat, S. and Black, B. (2002). The non-correlation between board independence and long-term firm performance. *Journal of Corporation Law*, 27, p231-273.

Bhagat, S. and Black, B. (2000). The Uncertain Relationship Between Board Composition and Firm Performance. *Business Lawyer*, 54, p921-963.

Bhagat, S., Carey, D.C., and Elson, C.M. (1999). Director Ownership, Corporate Performance, and Management Turnover. *Business Lawyer*, 54, p885-920.

Blue Ribbon Committee (BRC) (1999). Report and Recommendations of the Blue Ribbon Committee on Improving the Effectiveness of Corporate Audit Committees. New York Stock Exchange, New York, NY.

Bokpin, A. (2013). Ownership structure, corporate governance and bank efficiency: an empirical analysis of panel data from the banking industry in Ghana. *Corporate Governance*, 13(3), p274-287.

Bouaziz, Z. and Triki, M. (2012). The Impact of the Board of Directors on the Financial Performance of Tunisian Companies. *Universal Journal of Marketing and Business Research*, 1(2) p56-71.

Boyd, J. and Runkle, D. (1993). Size and Performance of Banking Firms: Testing the Predictions Theory. *Journal of Monetary Economics* 31, p47–67.

Cadbury, A. (1992). Report of the Committee on the Financial Aspects of Corporate Governance. London: Gee and Co., Ltd. (a division of Professional Publishing Ltd.).

Caprio, G., Laeven, L., and Levine, R. (2007). Governance and banks' valuations. *Journal of Financial Intermediation*, 16, p584-617.

Claessens, S., Djankov, S., and Pohl, G. (1997). Ownership and Corporate Governance: Evidence from the Czech Republic. Public Policy for the Private Sector. The World Bank Group, Note No. 111, May, p1-4.

Cole, R. and Mehran, H. (1998). The effect of changes in ownership structure on performance: evidence from the thrift industry. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 50, p291-317.

Dalton, D., Daily, C., Ellstrand, A., and Johnson, J. (1998). Meta-analytic reviews of board composition, leadership structure, and performance. *Strategic Management Journal*, 19, p269–290.

Davidson, W.N., Pilger, T., and Szakmary, A. (1998). Golden Parachutes, Board and Committee Composition and Shareholder Wealth. *The Financial Review*, p17-32.

Davis, J., Schoorman, F., and Donaldson, L. (1997). Towards a Stewardship Theory of Management. *Academy of Management Review*, 22, p20–47.

Demsetz, H. and Lehn, K. (1985). The structure of corporate ownership: causes and consequences. *Journal of Political Economy*, 93(6), p1155-1177.

Denis, D. and McConnell, J. (2003). International corporate governance. *Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*, 38(1), p1-36.

Eichengreen, B. and Gibson, H.D. (2001). Greek Banking at the Dawn of the New Millennium. CEPR Discussion Paper.

Eisenberg, T., Sundgren, S., and Wells, M. (1998). Large board size and decreasing firm value in small firms. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 48, p35-54.

Fama, E. (1980). Agency problems and the theory of the firm. *Journal of Political Economy*, 88, p288-307.

Farinha, J. (2003). Corporate governance: a survey of the literature. *Journal of Business Finance & Accounting*, 30(9-10), p1173–1209.

Field, A. (2009). *Discovering Statistics Using SPSS, Third Edition*. Sage Publications.

Fuentes, R. and Vergara, M. (2003). Explaining Bank Efficiency: Bank Size or Ownership Structure? Central Bank of Chile.

Godard, L. and Shatt, A. (2004). Characteristics and Functions of the French Administration *Caractéristiques et fonctionnement des d'administration français : Un état des lieux*», Cahier du FARGO, n° 104020, février.

Hall, B.J. and Liebman, J.B. (1998). Are CEOs Really Paid Like Bureaucrats? *Quarterly Journal of Economics* 113, p653-691.

Jensen, M. (1986). Agency costs of free cash-flow, corporate finance and takeovers. *American Economic Review*, 76, p323-329.

Jensen, M. and Meckling, W. (1976). Theory of the firm: managerial behaviour, agency costs and ownership structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3, p305-360.

Johnson, G., Scholes, K., and Whittington, R. (2008). *Exploring Corporate Strategy*, 8th Edition. Essex, England: Pearson Education Limited.

Karaca, S.S. and Eksi, I.H. (2012). The Relationship Between Ownership Structure and Firm Performance: An Empirical Analysis Over Istanbul Stock Exchange (ISE) Listed Companies. *International Business Research*, 5(1).

Klein, A. (1998). Firm Performance and Board Committee Structure. *Journal of Law and Economics*, 41, p275-303.

Kosmidou, K. (2008). The Determinants of Banks' Profits in Greece During the Period of EU Financial Integration. *Managerial Finance* 34(3), p146–159.

La Porta, R., Lopez-de-Silanes, F., Shleifer, A., and Vishny, R. (1998). Law and Finance. *Journal of Political Economy*, 106, p1113-1155.

Lehman, E. and Weigand, J. (2000). Does the Governed Corporation Perform Better? Governance Structures and Corporate Performance in Germany. *European Finance Review*, 4, p157-195. Kluwer Academic Publishers: The Netherlands.

Levine, R. (2004). The corporate governance of banks: a concise discussion of concepts and evidence. *World Bank Policy Research*, WPS3404.

Macey, J. and O'Hara, M. (2003). The corporate governance of banks. *Federal Reserve Bank of New York. Economic Policy Review*, p91-107.

Macus, M. (2008). Board capability: An interactions perspective on boards of directors and firm performance. *International Studies of Management & Organization*, 38(3), p98-116.

Miller, S.M. and Noulas, A. (1997). Portfolio Mix and Large Bank Profitability in the USA. *Applied Economics* 29, p505–512.

Mitchell, R., Agle, B., and Wood, D. (1997). Toward a theory of stakeholder identification and salience: defining the principle of who and what really counts. *Academy of Management Review*, 22(4), p853-886.

Nyamongo, E. and Temesgen, K. (2013). The effect of governance on performance of commercial banks in Kenya: a panel study. *Corporate Governance*, 13(3), p236–248.

Organization for Economic Co-Operation and Development (OECD). *Principles of Corporate Governance*. Paris: OECD publications (1998, 1999, and 2004).

Pasiouras, F. and Kosmidou, K. (2007). Factors Influencing the Profitability of Domestic and Foreign Commercial Banks in the European Union. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 21, p222–237.

Pathan, S., Skully, M., and Wickramanayake, J. (2008). Reforms in Thai Bank Governance: The Aftermath of the Asian Financial Crisis. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 17(2), p345-362.

Pathan, S., Skully, M., and Wickramanayake, J. (2007). Board Size, Independence and Performance: An Analysis of Thai Banks. *Asia-Pacific Financial Markets*, 14, p211-227.

Peni, E. and Vahamaa, S. (2012). Did Good Corporate Governance Improve Bank Performance During the Financial Crisis? *Journal of Financial Services Research*, 41(1-2), p19-35.

Pincus, K., Rusbarsky, M., and Wong, J. (1989). Voluntary Formation of Corporate Audit Committee Among NASDAQ Firms. *J. Account and Public Policy*, 8, p239-265.

Rabelo, F. and Vasconcelos, F. (2002). Corporate governance in Brazil. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 3, p321-335.

Ramsay, I. (2001). Ramsay Report: Independence of Australian Company Auditors: Review of Current Australian Requirements and Proposals for Reform. Corporate Governance and Accounting Policy Division, Department of the Treasury.

Rediker, K. and Seth, A. (1995). Board of directors and substitution effects of alternative governance mechanisms. *Strategic Management Journal*, 16, p85-99.

Sarbanes-Oxley Act (2002). Public Law 107-204. US Congress, 116 STAT., p745-810.

Shleifer, A. and Vishny, R. (1997). A Survey of Corporate Governance. *Journal of Finance*, 52, p737-783.

Spong, K.R. and Sullivan, R.J. (2007). *Corporate Governance and Bank Performance*. Glos, UK: Eduard Elgar Publishing Limited.

Stathopoulos, K., Espenlaub, S., and Walker, M. (2004). U.K. Executive Compensation Practices: New Economy versus Old Economy". *Journal of Management Accounting Research*, 16, p57-92.

Turnbull, S. (1997). Corporate governance: Its scope, concerns and theories. *Corporate Governance*, 5, p180-205.

Vancil, R.F. (1987). *Passing the Baton: Managing the Process of CEO Selection*. Harvard Business School Press, Boston, MA.

Yermack, D. (1996). Higher market valuation for firms with a small board of directors. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 40, p185-211.